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DISRUPTIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN LOGISTICS AND THEIR POSITIVE ENVIRONMENTAL CONSEQUENCES

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ÜNİVERSİTESİ

OUTLINE

- DISRUPTIVE TECHNOLOGIES
- ADVENT OF THE INTERNET
- THE DYNAMICS OF THE POST-DIGITAL ECOSYSTEM
- INTERNET OF THINGS
- 3D PRINTERS
- AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES
- BLOCKCHAIN

DISRUPTIVE TECHNOLOGIES

- **Disruptive innovation** creates a new market and value network and eventually disrupts an existing market and value network.
- A **disruptive technology** displaces an established technology and shakes up the industry and creates a completely **new industry**.
- Disruptive technologies cause the business processes to be **redesigned**.

ADVENT OF INTERNET

- After the rise of internet, **digital economy** has started to impact all sectors including retail, transports, financial services, manufacturing, education, culture, healthcare, and media industries.
- Internet brings about fertile ecosystem for the disruptive technologies.
- These technologies **eliminate many business lines** but do not create the same amount of jobs since it requires less labor.
- The **product life cycle** is getting shorter and technological developments are getting faster.

ADVENT OF INTERNET

- The most important **production factor** in digital economy is information.
- Today, regarding access to information, there are essential **differences** among individuals who has and has not accessed to the internet.
- This differences trigger consecutive inequalities.

THE DYNAMICS OF THE POST-DIGITAL ECOSYSTEM

- The **digital divide** refers to the unequal distribution of technological infrastructure usage within society.
- On the one hand, a **computer user** who takes advantage of communication possibilities.
- On the other hand, there is a **class devoid of basic communication facilities.**

THE DYNAMICS OF THE POST-DIGITAL ECOSYSTEM

- There is a relationship between **income level** and **internet access**.
- Today, all the **routine works** are taken over by machines.
- Therefore this causes **economic inequality**.

INTERNET OF THINGS

Intelligent Systems for a More Connected World

WHAT ARE INTELLIGENT SYSTEMS?

Intelligent Systems are devices that transform how we travel, shop, make things and more.

1) Cisco, "The Internet of Things: How the Next Evolution of the Internet is Changing Everything", April 2011
 2) Blair Research, "Security challenges in the US healthcare sector" White Paper, December 2010, <http://www.mcafee.com/resources/whitepapers/hg-blair-healthcare-security.pdf>
 3) Statista U.S., 2011 Annual Holiday Survey, http://www.statista.com/press/press-releases/2011/06/01/2011-annual-holiday-survey-2011_jr_102611.pdf
 4) McKinsey Global Institute analysis, "Big data: The next frontier for innovation, competition, and productivity", June 2011
 5) Wall Street Journal, <http://online.wsj.com/article/SB10001424052702304066504576345763614933644.html>, estimate from research firm, Frost & Sullivan

INTERNET OF THINGS

Warehouse Operation

Freight Transportation

Last Mile Delivery

INTERNET OF THINGS

Warehouse Operations

- Smart inventory management
- Damage detection
- Real time visibility
- Accurate inventory control

INTERNET OF THINGS

Sensors in Freight Transport

- Fleet Management
- Predictive Asset Maintenance

Image credit: <http://www.mouser.com>

INTERNET OF THINGS

Last Mile Delivery: IoT and Mail Delivery/Pickup

- Optimize mail pickup
- Notify customer of delivery
- Flexible delivery address
- Maximize return trip

INTERNET OF THINGS

Last Mile Delivery: IoT: Automatic replenishment and anticipatory shipping

- Smart Lockers
- Delivery on first attempt
- Tracking expiration dates
- Anticipate Orders

3D PRINTERS

3D PRINTERS

- Decentralize the production.
- Lead to **reduction in the shipping** and **air cargo volumes**.
- Reduction in warehouse requirement.
- Reduce carbon emission and reduce product carbon footprint

3D PRINTERS

Storage and warehousing are obligaliton

- Remove the need for warehouse, decrease the packaging cost
- less obsolescence of existing stock.
- It will accelerate a shift from **“push supply chains”** to **“pull supply chains.”**
- **Increase** customization.

AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES

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Daimler
Iveco
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AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES

Six brands of automated trucks have been driving in columns (platooning), on public roads from several European cities to the Netherlands.

Truck platooning will ensure **cleaner** and **more efficient transport**.

Self-driving vehicles also contribute to **road safety** because most accidents are caused by human failure

BLOCKCHAIN

- Blockchain Based Supply Network Management System
- Autonom & Distributed Trust Model

BLOCKCHAIN

BLOCKCHAIN

BLOCKCHAIN

- **Time savings:** Transaction settlement is faster because it doesn't require verification by a central authority.
- **Cost savings:** Intermediaries are eliminated.
- **Tighter security:** Protect against tampering, fraud, and cybercrime.
- **Enhanced privacy:** Users can specify which transaction details they want other participants to be permitted to view.
- **Improved auditability:** Ability to monitor and audit transactions.
- **Increased operational efficiency:** Facilitate the transactions.
- **Building trust:** Increasing the level of trust among network participants.

Summary

The background features a series of overlapping, 3D-style rectangular blocks in teal, dark blue, and yellow, arranged in a stepped pattern that recedes into the distance. The blocks are set against a white background with vertical grey lines that create a sense of depth and perspective.

THANK YOU